

Timestamp	date	MEASURES				NORMALISED			
		L1	L2	L3	L4	L1	L2	L3	L4
#1139	06/18/2020 - 18:19	7	9	12	4	0,375	0,625	1	0
#1141	06/18/2020 - 20:06	1	4	7	8	0	0,429	0,857	1
#1142	06/21/2020 - 17:37	1	3	9	7	0	0,25	1	0,75
#1143	06/21/2020 - 18:18	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	1
#1144	06/23/2020 - 12:46	6	11	11	9	0	1	1	0,6
#1146	06/24/2020 - 10:03	3	12	3	12	0	1	0	1
#1147	06/24/2020 - 10:48	5	9	3	11	0,25	0,75	0	1
#1148	06/24/2020 - 14:33	0	11	0	0	0	1	0	0
#1149	06/25/2020 - 12:07	3	6	14	12	0	0,273	1	0,818
#1153	07/03/2020 - 10:42	3	6	14	8	0	0,273	1	0,455
#1154	07/04/2020 - 11:14	10	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
#1155	07/06/2020 - 20:49	0	9	1	12	0	0,75	0,083	1
#1156	07/06/2020 - 22:38	0	14	14	0	0	1	1	0
#1158	07/09/2020 - 12:32	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0

DecideIT Midpoint	0,1875	0,5249	0,4957	0,5445
DecideIT Lower hull	0,0000	0,1276	0,0000	0,0931
DecideIT Upper hull	0,5503	0,9223	0,9996	0,9958